

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF USING OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Akbarova Mohichehra Rifatillayevna,

English teacher of the state conservatory of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article is intended to entirely describe the role of multimedia technology in modern education system, to show the importance of multimedia in teaching Russian, besides, in this article the main features and methods of developing multimedia projects will be mentioned.

Key words: multimedia technology, distance learning, multimedia computer, multimedia textbook, multimedia game, hypertext, electronic dictionary, interactive board, online mode, information resource

Modern system of education actively uses information technology and telecommunication computers. Especially, there is a dynamic development of distance learning system, which can promote further factors – provide educational institutions with high end computer technologies and development of cooperative Internet network.

The development of cutting edge technologies has brought new, unique chance of leading courses, introduction of distance forms of learning. First of all, it allow the users to choose time and place for learning, secondly, it opens up the opportunity to gain knowledge for people who are disabled to take traditional education because of some reasons, thirdly, using information technology, fourthly, to reduce the cost of education. On the other hand, distance learning can strengthen the opportunities of individual learning.

As a rule, electronic books are widely used in distance form of learning. The advantages of these books tend to be that they are mobile, secondly accessibility of networks with development of computer networks, thirdly, adequacy of level improvements of modern science. On the other hand, the creation of electronic books

may also trigger some solutions and problems, such as constant updating of information materials. They can also consist of large number of exercises and examples, to illustrate in detail different types of information in loudspeaker. Apart from that, with the help of electronic books can be implemented control over knowledge – computer testing.

Multimedia computer – it is not only integrated data medium, it is the tool that can fully and adequately represent model “face to face”. Besides, only in computers can be implemented information – reference system on the basis of hypermedia reference, it is also considered as one of the main parts of independent learning. Usually, multimedia books may represent the group of learners, that are controlling, modeling and other programs which are placed in magnetic carrier, in which represented the main scientific content of disciplines. Multimedia text-book is often supplement common on, specifically effective in cases when it: Provides practical instantaneous feedback; Can help to find needed information(including context search), the search which is complicated in usual textbooks; Considerably can save the time in repeated appeal to hypertext explanations; Along with short text it shows, tells, design and etc. (exactly in this place bring the opportunities and advantages of multimedia technology) allows to work fast, but in pace which is suitable for exact individual, to check knowledge by specific parts. Hypertext and hypermedia tools Hypertext – is the way of non-linear supplying of text materials, with the help of this can be seen some selected words, which have linkage to specific text fragments. In this way, users not only will turn over the pages of textbooks, but also can deviate from line description by some kinds of references, which means that the user can control over the information ex-change process. In the system of hypermedia pictures can be used as fragments, whereas data consist of text, graphics, video fragments, sound. Nowadays, there are various types of hypertext formats available (HTML, DHTML, PHP and etc.) [15; c 42-46]

Electronic dictionaries – it is the lexical information that systematized in specific way (data base of dictionary), which is saved in computers memory, but it

is also considered as the program for processing of information and presentation on the screen.

Electronic dictionaries connect some functions of interesting information searching demonstration of language regularities and gives the opportunity to master school materials with the help of some exercises.

On-line electronic dictionaries can be found in <http://www.chat.ru/~francais/language/diction.htm>. Such as, Multilex (electronic French-Russian and Russian-French dictionary, consist of more than 2500.000 words in Russian and French parts), Prompt (it is used for translation of applications from Russian into French and from French into Russian), Webster Dictionnaire (considered as one of the best dictionaries nowadays), Une vu – Diction-naire (electronic system of computer searching simultaneously in 112 dictionaries various subjects and directions), Lingvo (French – Russian and Russian – French dictionary, consist of 7000 words). In recent years, the usage of multimedia technology is being field effectively in all areas of teaching foreign language and during the lessons of participants from different group. Moreover, diversity of technologies in teaching allows to make the lessons more interesting and intriguing. This kind of approach can motivate learners in learning process, simplifies assimilating of foreign languages. For example, when working with hypertext learners not only turn over the page of textbook, but also can affect from line description by some references which means they themselves can control the process of information exchange.

Interactive board: The usage of projection technologies in combination of audio tools gives the chance of attract students in the lessons when explaining new resources theses, tables, videos and reference materials, when analyzing texts – schemes and the information of electronic dictionaries. It gives the opportunity to carry out visual aids, availability and systemic description of materials.

In context of the above truly revolutionary invention is considered to be interactive SMART Board. By using this kind of board, teacher can combine proved methods and the style of working with common board with the set of interactive and multimedia opportunities.

Electronic board SMART allows: Active commenting upon materials: highlighting, definition, adding extra information by means of electronic markers with the possibility of changing color and thickness of lines. Full – fledged translation in terms of text translation and separated sentences with stated connection and interrelations between words; With means of virtual keyboards any kinds of text tasks in any applications and its demonstration in the mode of real time. Not only familiarity with test tasks in browsing mode, but also demonstrative testing of separated books or groups of students for all classroom, In schools computer classes absent or they are not available for teacher use for the moment; Saving of results in various separated file in the form of pictures or in HTML and PDF-formats.

It should be signified that interactive board has positively impact on teaching foreign languages, as it is considered to be overt illustration of untraditional approach of teaching foreign languages. Teachers of a foreign language who have sufficient experience with an interactive whiteboard have identified for themselves its undoubted advantages:

- working with the board allows you to fully implement the principle of clarity;
- bright and attractive materials of the collection raise aesthetic taste in children;
- interactive board capabilities allow you to remove difficulties in the process of monologic utterance;
- The ability to cut and erase objects from the screen, copy and paste them, cancel or return actions gives students more confidence: they know that they can always go back a step, change or correct something.

Concisely, Interactive whiteboard features allowance for students to understand that video and game programs are successfully used for learning, contributing to the development of creative activity, fascination with the subject, and creating the best conditions for mastering listening and speaking skills, which ultimately ensures the efficiency of learning in foreign language lessons .

References:

1. Richards, J. C. (2001). The context of language teaching. Beijing: Foreign Languages Teaching and Research Press
2. Ellis, R. (1999). Understanding second language acquisition. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.